

SURVEY ON IDENTIFICATION OF CYBER
SECURITY CHALLENGES & PRACTICES
FROM VENDORS POINT OF VIEW IN THE
CONTEXT OF SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT
FOR CYBER SECURITY CHALLENGES
MODEL (CSCM)

Dear Sir / Madam,

We want your kind participation for our research work survey pointing out “challenges and practices in terms of cybersecurity from vendor’s perspective in software development.”

As we know that secure software development is very important factor for any vendor organization in Software Industry. The main objective of this study to explore the reasons and how should cyber-attacks take place and how much harmful can be these attacks. It will tell us about the negative factors of cyber-attacks on vendor organization in context of software development and also tell us about the solution to these negative factors. The ultimate goal of this research study is to develop a cyber-security challenges model (CSCM) that will facilitate the vendor organization to identify all those cyber security issues that have negative impact on vendor organization.

During this survey all the collected data will be used only for research purpose. Furthermore, all this information would be considered CONFIDENTIAL, in case of publication from this study information will present in aggregated form i.e. organization or individual respondent participant in the survey cannot be identified.

Your participation in this survey is voluntarily. In case of any concern about this survey, you can withdraw from this research project at any time.

In case of any query, you can contact Shah Zaib at +92-334-8685937 / email: shahzebbiseb@gmail.com or Dr. Abdul Wahid Khan (Supervisor) +92-334-8686258 / e-mail wahidkn@gmail.com

We will be very grateful for your participation in this survey. Thank you in advance for providing this important feedback.

Shah Zaib
MSCS Scholar
Department of Computer Science
University of Science & Technology, Bannu, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan
E-mail: shahzebbiseb@gmail.com
Cell No: +92-334-8685937

Dr. Abdul Wahid Khan
Assistant Professor
Department of Computer Science
University of Science & Technology Bannu, KPK, Pakistan
E-mail: wahidkn@gmail.com
Cell No: +92-334-8686258

1. SECTION ONE

1.1 Participant General Information

Name	Title	First Name	Last Name	Date Today	DD.MM.YYYY
Job Title/Position	Write your job title presently		Experience in Years	Job experience	
Organization	Write name of your organization please.				
Address	Write address of your organization please.				
E-mail	Write your E-mail please.			Cell No	Write contact No (Optional)

Have you ever been participated in any Software Development project in your Company which face the issues of cybersecurity/cyberattacks? Yes No If yes, please specify number of Projects: Please Specify

What was / is your role in team:

Developer Designer Team Leader Manager Analyst Other Please Specify

1.2 Organization Information

Company Country Please specify company country location.

What is the primary business of your company? (You may select (✓) more than one option)

In-house development Outsourcing Other Please specify.

What is the type of your company? (please tick (✓) as appropriate)

Multinational National Do not know Other Please specify

Approximately how many staff are employed by your company? (please tick (✓) as appropriate)

less than < 20 between 20 to 199 greater than or equal to ≥ 200

What type of systems is your company concerned with? (You may tick (✓) more than one)

- | | | | |
|--|---|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Safety Critical | <input type="checkbox"/> Business Systems | <input type="checkbox"/> Telecommunications | <input type="checkbox"/> Real-time Systems |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Data Processing | <input type="checkbox"/> Systems Software | <input type="checkbox"/> Windows Based | <input type="checkbox"/> Embedded Systems |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Web Development | <input type="checkbox"/> Mobile Applications
Development | <input type="checkbox"/> API Development | <input type="checkbox"/> Cloud Computing |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other | Please specify | | |

Your company relies on industry standards in order to select offshore vendor (e.g. CMMI)?

(please tick (✓) as appropriate)

- Yes No Do not know

What is the CMMI level for your company? Please Specify

Your company has the ability to preserve and manage relations with external IT vendors?

- Yes No Do not know

How confident are you in your organization's overall security posture? (Select one)

- Extremely confident Very Confident Moderately confident Slightly confident Not at all confident

What negative impact have security incidents had on your company in the past 12 months? (Select all that apply)

- | | | | |
|--|--|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Reduce revenue or lost business | <input type="checkbox"/> Disrupted business activities | <input type="checkbox"/> Reduced employee productivity | <input type="checkbox"/> Increased helpdesk time to repair damage |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Regulatory fines | <input type="checkbox"/> Lawsuit/legal issues | <input type="checkbox"/> Loss/compromise of intellectual property | <input type="checkbox"/> Corporate data loss/theft |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know/unsure | <input type="checkbox"/> None | <input type="checkbox"/> Other | |

2. SECTION TWO

2.1 Cyber Security Challenges Description

We have identified various challenges from literature review faced by vendor organizations in software development in the shape of cyber security. The identified challenges and their short description are given below:

Cyber Security Challenges	Description
Security Issues / Access of Cyber-attacks Challenge	Attacks are increasing and defecting the systems in very fast way and also occurrence of several crimes.
Lack of Right Knowledge Challenge	Intellectual Property Rights or Property Right Acts of the Software and also a Lack of Knowledge regarding product and policies.
Framework Challenge	Lack and unavailability of network computer protection and networks are vulnerable to attacks, Web Browsers or websites vulnerability and Framework used or illustrated.
Lack of Technical support Challenge	Lack of professional skills, training and technical support.
Disaster Issues Challenge	Failed in protection, detecting and preventing of attacks/vulnerabilities and data manipulation which causes disasters.
Cost Security Issues Challenge	Serious economic, investment and financial challenges.
Lack of Confidentiality and Trust Challenge	Lack of trust, lack of confidentiality and integrity and intractability which makes it more vulnerable to attacks.
Lack of Management Challenge	Lack of focus on necessary requirements and protection from vulnerabilities during software development, Management problems, Careless and unconstrained Behavior in development and protection from vulnerabilities.
Unauthorized Access Issues Challenge	Get access to information without authentication or any necessary process and

	lack of detection of source of threats.
Lack of Resources Challenge	Lack of resources or not used at the right place and time.
Lack of Metrics Challenge	Meaningful metrics, proactive cybersecurity measures and lack of impact or bad impact issues on software or in software development.
Administrative Mistakes during Development Challenge	Administrative mistakes/issues which results in vulnerabilities and also in loss of reputation of an organization.
Lack of Quality, Liability and Reliability Challenge	Lack of quality, liability and reliability during development of software.

2.2 Identify Cyber Security Challenges

Please tick (✓) appropriate box based on your experience.

Cyber Security Challenges	Agree	Not Sure	Disagree
Security Issues / Access of Cyber-attacks	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of Right Knowledge	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Framework	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of Technical support	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Disaster Issues	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cost Security Issues	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of Confidentiality and Trust	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of Management	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Unauthorized Access Issues	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of Resources	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of metrics	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Administrative Mistakes during Development	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of Quality, Liability and Reliability	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other: You can add other challenge which affect software development due to cyberattacks.			
i.			
ii.			

3. SECTION THREE

We have identified different practices from literature review for different cybersecurity challenges described in section 2.1. Detail of practices for each challenge is given below. Please tick (✓) appropriate box based on your experience.

3.1 Practices for Security Issues / Access of Cyber-attacks Challenge

Practice	Option
3.1.1 To introduce the concept of open-source product development.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.2 To use the anti-malware protection system to keep the software safe.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.3 To understand and evaluate the current security practices, regulations and standards.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.4 To advance vendor security concern, the price of security be included in the product.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.5 To protect the individuals and organization by applying Human and Organizational Security Knowledge Areas (KAs).	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.6 To use cryptographic concept for data sharing.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.7 To use Host Intrusion Detection Sensor (HID) mechanism for active defense.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure

	<input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.8 To use signature detection or multi-signature protection for privacy and security.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.9 To share in advance information about new threats and vulnerabilities for software protection.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.10 To create threat and vulnerability warning model.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.11 To use defense-in-breadth approach for mitigating attacks.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.12 To use code reviews for finding and fixing of security bugs.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.13 To use twin strategies of detection and response, risk analysis and application performance degradation identifying and analyzing vulnerabilities of the software.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.14 To use strong passwords and two-factor authentication for safe use of software.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.1.15 To use anomaly detection method for detecting anomalous behaviors or data.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree

Other: You can add other practices.
3.1.16
3.1.17

3.2 Practices for Lack of Right Knowledge Challenge

Practice	Option
3.2.1 To adopt and implement the strategies and technologies emerged from research activities for improvement in cybersecurity landscape.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.2.2 To share trend data about cyber incidents for effective strategic planning.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.2.3 To robust pipeline for cyber talent through different programs or academies.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.2.4 User awareness of cybersecurity and social responsibility to identify and handle threat properly.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.2.5 To enable ICT sector and government by sharing threat-based information to better protect critical systems.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.2.6 To reduce uncertainty, the collection of relevant historical data might have influence on software security.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree

3.2.7 To replace former dyad protection techniques with a triad of cyber protection capabilities.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.2.8 To publish a set of guidelines for secure software development.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
Other: You can add other practices.	
3.2.9	
3.2.10	

3.3 Practices for Framework Challenge

Practice	Option
3.3.1 To avoid potential targets of cyberstalking use Routine Activity Theory (RAT) framework.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.3.2 To create integrated, security aware software development environments.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.3.3 To use the four layers of protection cybersecurity strategy (preparedness, prevention, response and recovery).	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.3.4 To use virtual computing machines approach for protecting software and networks.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree

<p>3.3.5 To apply up to date software security patches for protection of organizations networks systems.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>3.3.6 To adopt NIST cybersecurity framework for protection of data in transit.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>Other: You can add other practices.</p>	
<p>3.3.7</p>	
<p>3.3.8</p>	

3.4 Practices for Lack of Technical Support Challenge

Practice	Option
----------	--------

3.4.1 To recognize the strategic importance of relationship between control systems and cybersecurity by professionals.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.4.2 To educate the professionals in multidisciplinary fields or sectors.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.4.3 To reconfigure Computer Science Courses to improve security in software development.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.4.4 Need of motivated and skilled cybersecurity professionals to prevent, detect, respond or mitigate the effect of threats.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.4.5 To develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills in addition to technical skills to asses, detect and identify threats.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.4.6 To use obfuscation technique to protect the software from attacks.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
Other: You can add other practices.	
3.4.7	
3.4.8	

3.5 Practices for Disaster Issues Challenge

Practice	Option
----------	--------

<p>3.5.1 To minimize total losses, disclose vulnerabilities and release fixes quickly.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>3.5.2 To use Fair Information Practice Principles and other privacy and civil liberties policies, practices and framework for protection of privacy.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>3.5.3 To establish incident-response practices for most critical and significant cybersecurity incidents.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>3.5.4 To design compensating controls to mitigate threat likelihood and/or impact severity.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>3.5.5 To use deception techniques/strategy for tracking of security incidents or distract attacker's attention.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>3.5.6 To use auto-analysis of legitimate usage patterns for recognition of malicious activities.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>Other: You can add other practices.</p>	
<p>3.5.7</p>	
<p>3.5.8</p>	

3.6 Practices for Cost Security Issues Challenge

Practice	Option
----------	--------

<p>3.6.1 To increase cost and use methods for empowering defenders to continue operation during an attack.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>3.6.2 To use monitoring cyber incidents and responses, soliciting and using standard terminology and measures for understanding cybersecurity economics.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>3.6.3 To maximize profit, the vendor needs to minimize expenditure on security.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>3.6.4 To use stock market returns to capture the direct and indirect costs of the information security breaches.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>3.6.5 To use cyber risk insurance policies as tool to provide coverage against losses/financial losses from internet related breaches.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>3.6.6 To understand effective IT governance prioritization and investment decision.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree</p>
<p>Other: You can add other practices.</p>	
<p>3.6.7</p>	
<p>3.6.8</p>	

3.7 Practices for Lack of Confidentiality and Trust Challenge

Practice	Option
----------	--------

3.7.1 To use cloud resources and artificial diversity technologies for protection.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.7.2 To use human-centricity approach to address the cybersecurity problem.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.7.3 To use prevention strategies to avoid information leakage, unauthorized access and modifications.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.7.4 To use a second threefold taxonomy for the protection of system.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.7.5 To use blockchain model to protect store information on computers.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.7.6 To protect the data of users on web browsers, it needs to be modified.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.7.7 To use data integrity verification method to save the data from tampering or being changed.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
Other: You can add other practices.	
3.7.8	
3.7.9	

3.8 Practices for Lack of Management Challenge

Practice	Option
3.8.1 To give controlling feedback of software to seller.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.8.2 To provide development and verification environment.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.8.3 To use human-centered and organizational development approaches for process of cybersecurity.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.8.4 To educate and train software managers for effective risk management.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.8.5 To create and share information by the employees in information management process.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.8.6 To create an atmosphere by the organizations that supports the development and maintenance of their expert staff.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
Other: You can add other practices.	
3.8.7	
3.8.8	

3.9 Practices for Unauthorized Access Issues Challenge

Practice	Option
3.9.1 To act quickly by vendors in the context of inevitable vulnerability.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.9.2 To use intrusion detection system to detect and counter measure the unauthorized access to a network or computer system.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.9.3 To use devices only prepared by the ICT team and sealed for protection of data.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.9.4 To use perimeter defense strategy i.e. firewalls and antivirus software to protect against unauthorized access or unauthorized information flow of the system.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.9.5 To enforce access control mechanisms to user privileges and restrict unauthorized use of resources and data.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.9.6 To perform cybersecurity audit for the best protection of information.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
Other: You can add other practices.	
3.9.7	
3.9.8	

3.10 Practices for Lack of Resources Challenge

Practice	Option
3.10.1 To estimate resource and design more secure systems, software managers need cause and effect information.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.10.2 To choose effective measures and organizational structures for efficiently use of resources.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.10.3 To compete with malicious attackers in vulnerability market for the purchase of vulnerabilities for defensive purpose.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.10.4 To develop and fill needs of a knowledgeable, sophisticated cybersecurity workforce, non-traditional background applicants should be hired.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.10.5 To use security gadgets to detect criminal mails in effective way.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
Other: You can add other practices.	
3.10.6	
3.10.7	

3.11 Practices for Lack of Metrics Challenge

Practice	Option
----------	--------

3.11.1 To require some punishment mechanism to force the vendor be at stake when an attack occurs.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.11.2 To stipulate goals, milestones, and metrics to measure and communicate the extent of progress in addressing the issues.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.11.3 To create principled approach to cybersecurity to prevent, detect and recover from an incident.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.11.4 To support the generation of secure code, provide reliable measurements and metrics for helping decision makers in development of secure application.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.11.5 To keep measurable and monitored security in entire network for considering good design.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.11.6 To avoid cyberattacks and minimize their impacts, use detection traced through a host system calls.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
Other: You can add other practices.	
3.11.7	
3.11.8	

3.12 Practices for Administrative mistakes during development Challenge

Practice	Option
----------	--------

3.12.1 To develop the capability to design, implement and evolve software and hardware systems which effectively manage risk, quality, cost and complexity.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.12.2 To create vulnerability market by using transferable security credits for balancing vulnerabilities in products.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.12.3 To create new tools for defense and hunt down hidden vulnerabilities in software and network through graduates.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.12.4 To increase security managers understandability by using surveillance.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.12.5 To use source code analysis for finding vulnerabilities at secure software development.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.12.6 To prevent virus infection by not sharing executable code with an infected source.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.12.7 To tend more care of data in traffic than stored data in software development.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
Other: You can add other practices.	
3.12.8	
3.12.9	

3.13 Practices for Lack of Quality, Liability and Reliability Challenge

Practice	Option
3.13.1 To use carrot-and-stick-like strategy to prevent software from vulnerability exploitation.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.13.2 To use Department of Defense (DoD) Software and others standards approaches to develop overall quality software.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
3.13.3 To create a checklist type cybersecurity review for proper encryption and updation of system.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree <input type="checkbox"/> Not Sure <input type="checkbox"/> Disagree
Other: You can add other practices.	
3.13.4	
3.13.5	

Summary of the cyber security challenges identified through empirical study

S.No	Challenges	Total Expert Responses = 35					
		Agree		Not Sure		Disagree	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	Security Issues/Access of Cyber Attacks	25	71	07	20	03	09
2	Lack of Right Knowledge	20	57	11	31	04	11
3	Framework	17	49	13	37	05	14
4	Lack of Technical Support	20	57	08	23	07	20
5	Disaster Issues	14	40	14	40	07	20
6	Cost Security Issues	17	49	14	40	04	11
7	Lack of Confidentiality and Trust	20	57	10	29	05	14
8	Lack of Management	24	69	06	17	05	14
9	Unauthorized Access Issues	22	63	07	20	06	17
10	Lack of Resources	17	49	12	34	06	17
11	Lack of Metrics	16	46	12	34	07	20
12	Administrative Mistakes during Development	15	43	09	26	11	31
13	Lack of Quality, Liability and Reliability	23	66	04	11	08	23

Distribution of security challenges identified through empirical study based on Organization Size

Challenges	Total Expert Responses = 35									Chi-Square Test (Linear-by-Linear Association) $\alpha = .05$		
	Organization Size									X ²	df	P
	Small (N=14)			Medium (N=08)			Large (N=13)					
	Agree	Not Sure	Dis Agree	Agree	Not Sure	Dis Agree	Agree	Not Sure	Dis Agree			
Security Issues/Access of Cyber Attacks	9	3	2	6	1	1	10	3	0	1.171	1	.279
Lack of Right	8	6	0	5	2	1	7	3	3	.948	1	.330

Knowledge												
Framework	8	5	1	4	4	0	5	4	4	2.256	1	.133
Lack of Technical Support	10	4	0	3	2	3	7	2	4	2.498	1	.114
Disaster Issues	6	5	3	3	3	2	5	6	2	.003	1	.960
Cost Security Issues	7	6	1	5	3	0	5	5	3	1.026	1	.311
Lack of Confidentiality and Trust	8	3	3	5	3	0	7	4	2	.012	1	.911
Lack of Management	1	2	1	4	2	2	9	2	2	.407	1	.523
Unauthorized Access Issues	10	2	2	6	2	0	6	3	4	1.872	1	.171
Lack of Resources	5	8	1	6	1	1	6	3	4	.183	1	.669
Lack of Metrics	7	6	1	3	3	2	6	3	4	.854	1	.356
Administrative Mistakes during Development	6	5	3	4	1	3	5	3	5	.411	1	.521
Lack of Quality, Liability and Reliability	9	1	4	5	1	2	9	2	2	.303	1	.582

Figure 1. Security Challenges identified through empirical study for CSCM from vendors perspective based on Company Size